

Horizontal Control Effector Sizing for High Speed Civil Transport *

Eric Hallberg †

Isaac Kaminer ‡

Abstract

This paper discusses the development of a numerical tool that determines the dynamic horizontal control effector sizing criteria for given High Speed Civil Transport dynamic model. This criteria includes computing the maximum cg travel for a range of control effector sizes and actuator motion constraints, while guaranteeing an existence of a feedback controller that will recover from a severe gust without exceeding actuator amplitude and rate limits and satisfy other dynamic requirements. The key idea is to formulate these constraints in terms of Linear Matrix Inequalities. This tool is termed the *Tail Sizing Design Tool*. In addition, the paper illustrates the application of the tool to measuring the effect of adding a second horizontal control surface in the form of a canard. The capability to measure the effect of simple, symmetric, flexible motion of the vehicle is also addressed. Based on numerical analysis of designs, conclusions are drawn on the relative effectiveness of the use of canards, the use of static versus dynamic controllers, and on the inclusion of aeroelastic effects.

1 Introduction

The use of an automatic flight augmentation system is commonplace on a modern aircraft. The benefits of its use may include such things as the remedy of undesirable flight characteristics, the reduction of pilot workload, and an increase in performance and fuel efficiency. Whether required for safe flight or not, it is hard to imagine a new transport aircraft being built without a sophisticated flight augmentation system. In fact, the next generation of high-speed civil transport (HSCT) aircraft will require some form of feedback control for safety of flight considerations, since current designs have an unstable short period.

Since HSCT will require some form of automatic flight control always being active, the sizing of its control surfaces is no simple matter. Traditionally, static constraints have been used to size the horizontal tail. For a given tail volume, constraints are calculated that limit the fore and aft travel of the center of gravity. Constraints that limit the forward center-of-gravity position include (1) sufficient nose-up pitch acceleration at the rotation speed (nose-wheel lift off), and (2) sufficient nose-up pitch acceleration at the approach speed in the landing configuration (go-around). Constraints that limit aft center-of-gravity position include (1) at brake release with maximum thrust, sufficient weight on the nose gear (tip back), (2) pitch-up acceleration at the rotation speed (nose-wheel lift off), and (3) sufficient nose-down pitch acceleration at minimum flying speeds [7].

At the aft center-of-gravity locations projected for the approach flight condition of the HSCT, dynamic constraints may be more restrictive than static constraints. The need to include dynamic considerations in the configuration definition process has been addressed before. References [3] and [2] describe early published work by Beaufre in this area, largely motivated by the X-29 research program. In [9], Schmidt uses the system sensitivity function to describe the fundamental trade-off that exists between the level of static instability that can be controlled and vehicle flexibility. Previous (unpublished) work in industry has used time domain analysis to determine how far aft (how unstable) the center of gravity could be before the airplane was unrecoverable. The analysis included a given design angle-of-attack disturbance, and given rate and position limits of the pitch control effector.

This work extends the work of [7], and uses a numerical technique similar to previous work in [8]. There an integrated aircraft controller design methodology using Linear Matrix Inequalities (LMI's) applied to the control power sizing for an F-14 aircraft. The major contribution of this work is twofold. First, the tail sizing design problem is defined in terms that include the integral participation of a feedback control system. Since the degree of control of the longitudinal dynamics depends on how fast and far the longitudinal control surface(s) can be moved by the control actuator(s), a natural metric that captures the *size* of the automatic flight control system is the maximum actuator rate. The design trade-off naturally includes consideration of actuator performance. For instance, it may be more cost effective to incorporate faster, generally larger and more expensive, actuators rather than pay the drag penalty associated with a larger horizontal tail. In that light, we introduce the following definition.

Tail Sizing Design Space: *The Tail Sizing Design Space is the region of "acceptable" combinations of tail volume (\bar{V}_H), center-of-gravity station ($x_{c.g.}$), and peak actuator rate (\dot{u}_{max}). The triplet $\{\bar{V}_H, x_{c.g.}, \dot{u}_{max}\}$, defines an aircraft model and an automatic flight control system. The model is obtained through the linearization of the nonlinear dynamics of the HSCT at an equilibrium point. It is partially defined by the specified tail volume and center-of-gravity position. The automatic flight control system is characterized by the specified maximum actuator rate in the triplet. By "acceptable" it is meant that, for the model associated with the triplet $\{\bar{V}_H, x_{c.g.}, \dot{u}_{max}\}$, a linear controller is known to exist that 1) stabilizes the plant, 2) meets prescribed dynamic performance constraints, and 3) does not exceed the maximum actuator rate in response to the dynamic constraint.*

The paper begins with the discussion of *Tail Sizing Design Tool* developed for a rigid-body HSCT model. The dynamic constraint associated with the problem is a se-

*This work was supported by NASA Langley Research Center under Contract No. L65444D.

† Department of Aeronautical and Astronautical Engineering, Naval Postgraduate School, Monterey, CA 93943, USA.

vere angle-of-attack disturbance. Numerical results follow based on an application of the *Tail Sizing Design Tool* to an HSCT model representative of current designs. Then, a method is developed that models the effects of simple, symmetric, flexible motion of the HSCT. Numerical results follow based on applying the *Tail Sizing Design Tool* to an aeroelastic HSCT model. Comparisons to the rigid-body model are made. The paper ends with conclusions and recommendations. All the numerical results presented in this paper were obtained using the Linear Matrix Inequality Toolbox [5].

2 Problem Formulation for a Rigid Body HSCT

The *Plant Controller Optimization* (PCO) problem to be solved in this section can be stated as follows: *Let an HSCT flight condition be specified by the aircraft's flight speed, altitude, and flight path angle. Furthermore, let a certain set of flying quality requirements exist for the HSCT at that flight condition. Let the dynamic constraint be defined as the recovery of the aircraft from a high angle-of-attack excursion, while not exceeding certain peak actuator rate and actuator amplitude limits. Then, for a range of horizontal tail volumes, and for a range of peak actuator rates, determine the aft center-of-gravity limits for which there still exists a linear feedback controller that 1) stabilizes the plant, 2) satisfies the flying quality and dynamic requirements, 3) meets actuator rate constraints.*

Let x_{cg} denote the center-of-gravity location as a fraction of the reference chord, and let x denote the vector of HSCT longitudinal states. Let u denote the horizontal tail incidence angle, and let \bar{V}_H denote the tail volume. Figure 1 provides a description of the tail volume, \bar{V}_H .

Figure 1: Definition of \bar{V}_H .

This representation is convenient since, for one flight condition, the wing-body mean aerodynamic center remains constant. Thus, the control surface volume and center of gravity are decoupled in terms of their influence on the vehicle's dynamics. The longitudinal dynamics of the aircraft can be expressed by the following system of differential equations:

$$\mathcal{G} = \begin{cases} \dot{x} &= \mathcal{F}(x, u, x_{cg}, \bar{V}_H), \\ z &= \mathcal{H}(x, u), \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where $\mathcal{F}(\cdot)$ is a C^1 function of x, u, x_{cg}, \bar{V}_H , \mathcal{H} is a C^1 function relating x and z , and $z = [V_T \ \gamma]^T$ defines the true airspeed (V_T) and flight path angle (γ). Let x_0, u_0 denote the trim values of x and u for a given z_0 and center-of-gravity location, x_{cg_0} , i.e. $\mathcal{F}(x_0, u_0, x_{cg_0}, \bar{V}_{H_0}) = 0$ and

$\mathcal{H}(x_0, u_0) = z_0$. Here the vector z is used to characterize the flight condition. Later, when x_{cg} is allowed to change, the trim values, x_0 and u_0 , will be recomputed for given values of x_{cg_0}, z_0 and \bar{V}_{H_0} . Appending the actuator dynamics in series to the linearization of longitudinal dynamics \mathcal{G} results in the linear system $\mathcal{G}_l(z_0, x_{cg_0}, \bar{V}_{H_0})$.

Flying quality requirements are typically characterized by the level of attention and skill required of the pilot to control the aircraft. They are grouped in three levels. A lower level corresponds to more benign flight characteristics. In order to achieve certain Level II flying qualities requirements, the eigenvalues of \mathcal{G}_l must be placed in a more restrictive region in the left half plane. Figure 2 shows suggested locations of the Category B, closed-loop pole locations of the HSCT short-period mode. These locations meet Level II flying quality requirements for the flight condition used in this study. Notice, these locations can be characterized as having a minimum damping ratio of 0.2 and natural frequency of 0.2 radians per second. This suggests that, in order to meet Level II requirements for the HSCT, the short-period eigenvalues of the closed-loop system \mathcal{G}_l must be placed in the region in the complex plane given by Figure 2.

Figure 2: Region \mathcal{L} for Level II Flying Qualities

2.1 Canard Configuration

The horizontal tail is the most significant control effector for longitudinal control of the aircraft. It is not uncommon, however, for long, slender aircraft designs to include canards for supplemental longitudinal control. The XB-70 and B-1B are two examples. Their presence is usually attributed to flying quality control issues involving the flexible nature of these aircraft [1]. This point is addressed in a subsequent section concerning control of an aeroelastic aerodynamic model. To lay the ground work for that section, and as a baseline point of comparison for a rigid structure, this section addresses the addition of a longitudinal control effector forward of the wing. The effect on the *Tail Sizing Design Space* is explored when the feedback control system is free to utilize both control surfaces, in order to recover from angle-of-attack excursions.

The revisions to the nonlinear equations of motion required to account for the addition of the canard parallel the development in [4]. The linearization of these nonlinear equations of motion about the equilibrium point determined by $(z_0, x_{cg_0}, \bar{V}_{H_0}, \bar{V}_{C_0})$, combined with the actuator dynamics for both the canard and horizontal tail results in the linear system $\mathcal{G}_l(z_0, x_{cg_0}, \bar{V}_{H_0}, \bar{V}_{C_0})$.

The initial condition is defined by the angle-of-attack perturbation. Let the angle-of-attack perturbation be

given as α_0 ; then the initial condition is

$$\delta x = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & V_i \cos(\alpha_0) & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}^T.$$

For each design point, $\mathcal{G}_l(z_0, x_{cg_0}, \bar{V}_{H_0}, \bar{V}_{C_0})$, the question becomes, is the set of feedback controllers that recover the aircraft from the angle-of-attack excursion, while maintaining acceptable flying qualities, and without saturating the actuator, or exceeding a certain actuator rate, empty?

2.2 Proposed Numerical Solution

In this section, we propose a numerical solution to the problem at hand. It was shown that when the plant parameters are fixed [6], the problem can be formulated in terms of an LMI, which is affine in both the controller parameters and actuator limits. *Minimizing the actuator rate limit is a convex optimization problem that can be solved exactly.* For one set of plant parameters, let the result of the process be characterized by the final values of all of the parameters. Repeat the process for different sets of values of the plant parameters. Then, an assumption is made that the points lie on a smooth hypersurface. If the grid of plant parameters is sufficiently fine, the shape of the hypersurface can be discerned. The projection of the hypersurface onto the three dimensional space spanned by tail volume, center-of-gravity location, and actuator rate limit defines a surface in the *Tail Sizing Design Space* that is extremely useful in the design of the aircraft.

Let Φ_1 denote an LMI feasibility set that, if non-empty, guarantees an existence of a state-feedback controller that for fixed $z_0, x_{cg_0}, \bar{V}_{H_0}, \bar{V}_{C_0}$, $u_{h_{max}}, \dot{u}_{h_{max}}, u_{c_{max}}, \dot{u}_{c_{max}}$, stabilizes the linear plant, satisfies the flying quality requirements, meets the dynamic constraints. Similarly, we define Φ_2 to be the LMI feasibility set of output feedback controllers. Detailed definitions of these sets were omitted due to lack of space and can be found in [6].

Now, the *Plant Controller Optimization (PCO)* problem considered in this section can be stated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Maximize } \{x_{cg}\} \\ & \text{Subject to:} \\ & \mathcal{F}(X_0, U_0, x_{cg}, \bar{V}_{H_0}, \bar{V}_{C_0}) = 0, \mathcal{H}(X_0, U_0) = z_0, \\ & (Y, W) \in \Phi_1, \\ & \text{or } (\bar{A}_k, \bar{B}_k, \bar{C}_k, R, S) \in \Phi_2. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

A solution to this PCO problem includes a linear controller that stabilizes the feedback system $\mathcal{G}_l(z_0, x_{cg_0}, \bar{V}_{H_0}, \bar{V}_{C_0})$, and meets actuator limit requirements, as well as a maximum achievable aft center-of-gravity location.

The numerical solution used to map the *Tail Sizing Design Space* involved a binary search over center-of-gravity stations [6].

2.3 Results - Rigid Body HSCT

This design methodology was applied to a number of aerodynamic models representative of current high-speed civil transport designs. The results are shown for the aerodynamic model termed Ref A (see Appendix A in [6]). Appendix A details how a convenient build-up of the nonlinear longitudinal dynamics in terms of wing-body and tail contributions facilitates the process of mapping the *Tail Sizing Design Space*.

The state feedback synthesis LMIs (set Φ_1) were used. The data was obtained by the *Tail Sizing Tool* for a range

of tail volumes from 0.1 to 0.3, and a range of peak actuator rates from 5 to 40 degrees per second for HSCT model with and without canards, see Figure 3. Here each surface represents a lower bound on the peak actuator rate required by the feedback control system to recover from the angle-of-attack excursion, for various combinations of center-of-gravity location and tail volume. An upper bound in the *Tail Sizing Design Space* would be a fixed limit on the peak actuator rate available. Figure 3 also shows the inclusion of this plane for a value of 15 degrees per second. The volume below the plane and above each curved surface represents the *Tail Sizing Design Space*, where linear state-feedback controllers are known to exist that meet design requirements. Figure 4 shows a slice of the two surfaces in Figure 3 at a peak actuator rate limit of 15 degrees per second. This should be familiar as a conventional scissors plot. Of course, as one would expect, the design space increases with the additional control power available from the canard. The pertinent question is whether or not there is any benefit in spreading the control power for and aft, so to speak, or if the *Tail Sizing Design Space* would have increased just as much had the tail volume alone been increased by 0.05, and the canard not added. In general, it makes more sense to compare the competing configurations in terms of equal amounts of combined horizontal tail and canard surface area. For instance, profile drag is more closely related to the surface area of the control surfaces, among other things, and the design goal might be to minimize drag for the same aft center-of-gravity station and actuator rate limit. For this example, which utilized the Ref A data [6], the distance from the vehicle's wing-body neutral point to the aerodynamic center of the canard or horizontal tail was the same. Therefore, comparisons in terms of normalized area or volume are equivalent. It was determined that for the rigid-body HSCT model the benefit gained from the inclusion of a canard is about a 10 percent savings in total control volume.

Figure 3: *Tail Sizing Design Space* With and Without a Canard

3 Problem Formulation - Aeroelastic Model

The development of an integrated aeroelastic aerodynamic model followed well documented in work by Waszak and Schmidt [10]. There nonlinear equations of motion were derived using a Lagrangian approach and some standard simplifying assumptions. The elastic deformation was assumed to be sufficiently small such that linear elastic theory holds. The nonlinear aeroelastic equations of

Figure 4: 2D Slice of Tail Sizing Design Space With and Without a Canard

Figure 5: Tail Sizing Design Space Comparison: Canard On and Off

motion were linearized at an equilibrium point determined by the flight condition, canard volume, tail volume, and center of gravity.

Using Ref A model [6], the behavior of a rigid-body HSCT aircraft is compared with an aeroelastic model with the first elastic mode retained. The frequency separation between the elastic mode and the short period dynamics is approximately 1 Hertz, and the damping of the flexible mode is only 0.02. Typically, attempts are made to attenuate the feedback prior to excitation of the flexible dynamics. On large transport aircraft with the flexible dynamics close in frequency to the short period dynamics, this is hardly possible. Furthermore, even if suitable notch or low-pass filtering within the control loop could be attained, the extremely light damping of the flexible modes results in problems in terms of gust-induced structural responses and fatigue life. Therefore, the problem posed will be one of actively controlling the flexible modes retained. Generally, this will entail improving the damping of the flexible dynamics, while ensuring stability of the short period dynamics as the center of gravity is moved aft.

As before, actuator dynamics were appended to the aeroelastic model. The Plant-Controller Optimization problem formulation is exactly the same as discussed in section 2.

3.1 Results - Aeroelastic Model

The results are shown for the aeroelastic dynamic model termed Ref B in Appendix A [6]. Ref B model utilizes the same rigid-body stability and control derivatives as Ref A. The effect of a single, symmetric, flexible mode was incorporated. Once again, the LMI based *Tail Sizing Design Tool* was used to study the effect of the addition of a canard to the aeroelastic model. As before, a canard volume of 0.05 was selected, and the design space was determined. Figure 5 compares the design space of the aeroelastic model with and without the canard. Figure 6 shows the resulting aft line on the tail volume sizing plot when the two are cut at a peak actuator rate of 25 degrees per second. Of course, the added control volume due to the canard allows a further aft center-of-gravity location for a similar actuator rate limit.

The relative effect of adding a canard is addressed by comparing the total control volume, $(\bar{V}_H + \bar{V}_C)$, required for a given aft center-of-gravity limit and peak actuator rate limit. The results are shown in Figure 7 as a percent

Figure 6: 2D Comparison: Canard On and Off

reduction in control volume required in going from the configuration without a canard to the configuration with a canard. Since the lengths of the tail and canard moment arms are the same, Figure 7 could also represent a savings in total control effector surface area. Experience has shown that the use of canards is desirable for flexible aircraft [1]. This method provides a metric to quantify that benefit. In this example, the inclusion of a canard is 300 percent more effective when added to the aeroelastic model than when added to the rigid-body model.

As before, the process was repeated using the output feedback LMIs. The results utilizing the aeroelastic model support the conjecture that dynamic controllers of the same order as the plant do no better than static, state-feedback controllers. A representative comparison is shown in Figure 8. There the aft center-of-gravity stations are shown for a range of tail volumes and fixed canard volume. The peak actuator rate limit was 40 degrees per second.

4 Conclusions

The sizing of the horizontal control surface(s) for HSCT is a difficult problem. Traditionally, aircraft design has taken place apart from feedback considerations. Controller design was a derivative process, with little contribution to the aircraft definition. Of course, the aircraft were statically stable, and feedback control was viewed as a significant enhancement but not flight critical. This is an interesting example of an application where traditional

Figure 7: Decrease In Total Control Volume Through the Addition of a Canard

Figure 8: 2D Tail Sizing Design Space Comparison: Static versus Dynamic Controller on an Aeroelastic Model

methods simply lack the necessary tools to adequately define the aircraft configuration. Clearly, the aircraft definition will come first. However, it must be done with tools that provide a quantifiable knowledge of the impact on the demands of the feedback control system.

The most intuitive metric to select, capturing the demands of the feedback control system, is the peak actuator rate required. The inclusion of this metric adds an extra dimension to the tail sizing problem. The two dimensional tail sizing scissors plot is inadequate, and a natural extension is the Tail Sizing Design Space. A conventional scissors plot can be recovered by viewing the intersection of the Tail Sizing Design Space with a level plane. However, the three dimensional space allows the designer to see how sensitive the aft boundary is to changes in actuator rate. Clearly, there is value in knowing when small changes in the center-of-gravity location result in large changes in the actuator rate required.

While not solvable analytically, new efficient algorithms make the problem tractable numerically. A new design tool is provided that provides the capability to quickly determine the Tail Sizing Design Space for a given aircraft configuration. This paper demonstrates that many tail sizing problems can be formulated as LMIs, and exploit new interior point algorithms to obtain exact numerical solutions. The iterative nature of the design process requires a tool that can generate solutions in a timely

manner. Using the Tail Sizing Design Tool, the user can make adjustments to the aircraft definition, and quantifiably assess the impact on the demands of the feedback control system.

In this paper, two fundamental changes in aircraft definition were explored. Their influence on the Tail Sizing Design Space for a representative model of an HSCT was quantified. The first was the use of canards in addition to a horizontal tail. The second was the effect of simple, flexible motion. Additionally, the effect of using a static, state-feedback controllers, or dynamic, full-state, output-feedback controllers, was investigated for each element in the matrix.

Numerical results suggest that canards provide a small benefit for a rigid body HSCT. They are more effective when used on a flexible body HSCT. The metric used to assess their effectiveness was the change in total horizontal control volume. In this example, an aeroelastic model realized a reduction in total horizontal control volume of approximately 30 percent through the use of a canard. The rigid-body model realized a reduction in total horizontal control volume of approximately 10 percent. The use of a dynamic, full-state, output-feedback controller did not improve the results.

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